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METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF PERINDOPRIL AND INDAPAMIDE IN TABLET BY RP-HPLC METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A few methods are reported for prerequisite of telmisartan in biological samples and spectrophotometric estimation in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation. Also methods have been reported for qualification of atorvastatin by HPLC, RP HPLC, voltametry and derivative spectrophotometry. But no methods reported for the simultaneous determination of Perindopril and Indapamide in bulk and dosage form. The objective of this work was to develop and validate simple rapid and accurate chromatographic methods determination of Perindopril and Indapamide in tablet dosage form. The method was based on reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography, on inertsil ODS column 250x4.6mm using Phosphate buffer: ACN: methanol (40:25:35; v/v/v) pH 4.5 as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1ml/min at ambient temperature. The mean retention time of Perindopril and Indapamide was found to be 2.350 and 3.490 min respectively. The method was validated in terms of its linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, ruggedness, LOD and LOQ. This method can be used for routine quality control analysis due to its simplicity and accuracy.

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INTRODUCTION

Perindopril is a nonsulphydryl prodrug that belongs to the angiotensin converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitor class of medication. It is rapidly metabolized in the liver to perindoprilat, its active metabolite, following oral administration. Perindoprilat is a potent, competitive inhibitor of ACE, the enzyme responsible for the conversion of angiotensin-I (AT-I) to angiotensin-II (AT-II). AT-II regulates blood pressure and is a key component of the Rennin Angiotensin Aldosterone System (RAAS). Perindopril may be used to treat mild to moderate essential hypertension, mild to moderate congestive heart failure and to reduce the cardiovascular risk of individuals with hypertension or post myocardial infarction and stable coronary disease.

Indapamide is an oral antihypertensive/diuretic. Its molecule contains both a polar sulfamoyl chlorobenzamide moiety and a lipid-soluble methylindoline moiety. It differs chemically from the thiazides in that it does not possess the thiazide ring system and contains only one sulfonamide group.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and Reagents:

Perindopril and indapamide procured from Torrent Research Centre, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India Water (HPLC grade), Acetonitrile (HPLC grade), Di potassium hydrogen ortho phosphate (AR grade) Methanol (HPLC grade), Potassium dihydrogen ortho Phosphate (AR grade) were obtained from Merck Chemicals, Mumbai and Rankem Chemicals, Mumbai.

Apparatus and instrument:

Model: Shimadzu HPLC, Pump: LC-20AT VP, Column: Kromosil C18 column (250×4.6mm× 5μ), Detector: UV Detector, Syringe: Hamilton, Software: Spinchrom, Electronic balance: Shimadzu.

Mobile Phase:

A mixture of 60 volumes of Ammonium dihydrogen ortho phosphate buffer (pH 2.8): 40 volumes of Acetonitrile. The mobile phase was sonicated for 10min to remove gases.

Preparation of buffer (550ml):

1.6250gm of KH_2PO_4 was dissolved in 100ml of water and volume was made up to 100ml with water. Adjust the pH to 2.8 using orthophosphoric acid. The buffer was filtered through 0.45μ filters to remove all fine particles and gases.

METHOD VALIDATION:

VALIDATION:

HPLC method was validated for System suitability, Specificity by Direct comparison method, Linearity and range, Accuracy, Precision, Limit of Detection, Limit of Quantification, Robustness and Ruggedness.

System Suitability:

Standard solutions were prepared as per the test method and injected into the chromatographic system. The system suitability parameters like theoretical plates, resolution and asymmetric factor were evaluated.

Specificity:

There is no interference of mobile phase, solvent and placebo with the analyte peak and also the peak purity of analyte peak which indicate that the method is specific for the analysis of analytes in their dosage form.^[1,2]

Preparation of Samples for Assay:

Standard Sample:

Standard stock solutions of Perindopril and Indapamide (μg/ml) were prepared by dissolving 80mg of Perindopril and 25mg of Indapamide dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5min and dilute to 100 ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 80 μg/ml of Perindopril and 25 μg/ml of Indapamide was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.

Tablet Sample:

10tablets (Each tablet contains 2 mg of Perindopril and 0.625 mg of Indapamide) were weighed and taken into a mortar uniformly mixed. Test stock solutions of Perindopril (80μg/ml) and Indapamide (25μg/ml) were prepared by dissolving weight equivalent to 80mg of Perindopril and 25 mg of Indapamide and dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5 min and dilute to 100ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 80μg/ml of Perindopril and 25 μg/ml of Indapamide was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.^[3,4]

Linearity and range:**Preparation of mixed standard stock solution:**

Standard stock solutions of Perindopril and Indapamide ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared by dissolving 80mg of Perindopril and 25mg of Indapamide dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45 micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5min and dilute to 100ml with mobile phase and further dilutions.

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the method was determined by recovery studies. To the formulation (pre analyzed sample), the reference standards of the drugs were added at the level of 80%, 100%, 120%. The recovery studies were carried out three times. To check the accuracy of the method, recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard drug solution to pre-analyzed sample solution at three different levels 80%, 100%, 120%.^[4-6]

Precision:

Precision is the variability in the data from replicate determinations of the same homogeneous sample under the normal assay conditions

Method precision:

Prepared sample preparations of Perindopril and Indapamide as per test method and injected 6 times into the column.

Limit of Detection:

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value.^[7]

Limit of Quantification:

The quantification limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The quantification limit is a parameter of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample matrices, and is used particularly for the determination of impurities and/or degradation products.

Robustness:**Chromatographic conditions variation:**

To demonstrate the robustness of the method, prepared solution as per test method and injected at different variable conditions like using different conditions like Temperature and wavelength. System suitability parameters were compared with that of method precision.

Ruggedness:

The Ruggedness of an analytical method is definite by the analysis of aliquots from homogeneous lots in distinct laboratories, by contradictory analysts, using operational and environmental condition that may be at variance but are still within the particular parameters of the assay. The degree of reproducibility of the result is then determined as a function of assay variables. This reproducibility may be compared to the precision of assay under normal condition to obtain a measure of the ruggedness of the analytical method.^[8-12]

RESULTS:

Perindopril: Practically insoluble in water but soluble in methanol and ethanol.

Indapamide: Soluble in water, DMSO and Methanol.

Solubility Studies: These studies are carried out at 25 °C

Determination of Working Wavelength (λ_{max}):

In simultaneous estimation of two drugs isobestic wavelength is used. Isobestic point is the wavelength where the molar absorptivity is the same for two substances that are interconvertible. So this wavelength is used in simultaneous estimation to estimate both drugs accurately.

Preparation of standard stock solution of Perindopril:

25 mg of Perindopril was weighed and transferred in to 250ml volumetric flask and dissolved in methanol and then make up to the mark with methanol and prepare 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of solution by diluting 1ml to 10ml with methanol.

Preparation of standard stock solution of Indapamide:

25mg of **Indapamide** was weighed in to 250ml volumetric flask and dissolved in Methanol and then dilute up to the mark with methanol and prepare 10 µg/ml of solution by diluting 1ml to 10ml with methanol.

The wavelength of maximum absorption ($\lambda_{\max}$) of the drug, 10 µg/ml solution of the drugs in methanol were scanned using UV-Visible spectrophotometer within the wavelength region of 200–400 nm against methanol as blank. The resulting spectra are shown in the fig. no.1 and the absorption curve shows characteristic absorption maxima at 233 nm for Perindopril at 254 nm and Indapamide at 294 nm for the combination.

Figure 1: UV-VIS Spectrum of Perindopril, Indapamide and the Isosbestic Points.

Figure 2: Calibration graphs of Perindopril.

Figure 3: Calibration graphs of Indapamide.

Table 1: Results for calibration graph.

S. No.	PERINDOPRIL		INDAPAMIDE	
	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Peak Area	Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Peak Area
1	48	133.170	15	5320.620
2	64	182.347	20	6487.143
3	80	219.415	25	7831.788
4	96	269.912	30	9283.107
5	112	313.548	35	10235.854
S.D.	25.3	71	7.9057	2000
Slope	28.0		252.53	

Method Development of Perindopril and Indapamide:

Trial - 1:

Preparation of mixed standard stock solution:

Weigh accurately 80 mg of Perindopril and 25 mg of Indapamide in 100 ml of volumetric flask and dissolve in 10ml of mobile phase and make up the volume with mobile phase. From above stock solution 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Perindopril and 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Indapamide is prepared by diluting 5ml to 50ml with mobile phase. This solution is used for recording chromatogram.

Observation:

The peak Asymmetry factor was less than 2 for both Perindopril and Indapamide and the efficiency also good, and the retention time was also satisfactory for both Perindopril and Indapamide. The details are given in the table 8.3.4 and figure 8.3.4, hence it was taken for optimization.

Figure 4: Chromatogram of Perindopril and Indapamide by using Mobile Phase.

Table 2: Result of Perindopril and Indapamide by using mobile phase.

S.No.	Name	Rt (min)	Peak Area	Asymmetry	Efficiency	Resolution
1	Perindopril	2.463	193.706	1.012	2989	-
2	Indapamide	4.317	7826.434	1.56	3963	6.888

Assay:

Preparation of samples for Assay:

Standard sample:

Standard stock solutions of Perindopril and Indapamide ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) were prepared by dissolving 80 mg of Perindopril and 25 mg of Indapamide dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5min and dilute to 100 ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Perindopril and 25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Indapamide was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.

Tablet sample:

10tablets (Each tablet contains 2 mg of Perindopril and 0.625 mg of Indapamide) were weighed and taken into a mortar uniformly mixed. Test stock solutions of Perindopril (80 μ g/ml) and Indapamide (25 μ g/ml) were prepared by dissolving weight equivalent to 80mg of Perindopril and 25 mg of Indapamide and dissolved in sufficient mobile phase. After that filtered the solution using 0.45-micron syringe filter and Sonicated for 5 min and dilute to 100ml with mobile phase. Further dilutions are prepared in 5 replicates of 80 μ g/ml of Perindopril and 25 μ g/ml of Indapamide was made by adding 1 ml of stock solution to 10 ml of mobile phase.

Figure 5: Chromatogram of Assay standard preparation.

Figure 6: Chromatogram of Assay sample preparation.

Table 3: Assay Results of Perindopril and Indapamide.

PERINDOPRIL	INDAPAMIDE			
	Standard Area	Sample Area	Standard Area	Sample Area
Injection-1	193.706	192.454	7826.434	7716.294
Injection-2	195.827	197.776	7818.800	7829.617
Injection-3	195.161	232.244	7827.481	8109.044
Injection-4	211.310	211.418	8127.142	8311.593
Injection-5	225.128	214.801	8349.883	8280.792
Average Area	204.226	209.739	7989.948	8049.468
Tablet average weight	75		75	
Standard weight	80		25	
Sample weight	3000		3000	
Label amount	2		0.625	
Std. Purity	99.2		99.3	
Amount found in mg	2.04		0.63	
Assay(%purity)	101.88		100.04	

Observation:

The amount of Perindopril and Indapamide present in the taken dosage form was found to be 101.88 % and 100.04 % respectively.

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION:

A simple and selective LC method is described for the determination of Perindopril and Indapamide tablet dosage forms. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a ODS column using mobile phase consisting of an Ammonium dihydrogen ortho Phosphate buffer (KH₂PO₄) pH: 2.8: Acetonitrile. (60:40v/v), with detection of 233 nm. Linearity was observed in the range 48-112µg /ml for Perindopril (R² =0.998) and 15-35µg /ml for Indapamide (R² =0.996) for the amount of drugs estimated by the proposed methods was in good agreement with the label claim.

The proposed methods were validated. The accuracy of the methods was assessed by recovery studies at three different levels. Recovery experiments indicated the absence of interference from commonly encountered pharmaceutical additives. The method was found to be precise as indicated by the repeatability analysis, showing % RSD less than 2. All statistical data proves validity of the methods and can be used for routine analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form.

CONCLUSION

From the above experimental results and parameters it was concluded that, this newly developed method for the simultaneous estimation of Perindopril and Indapamide was found to be simple, precise, accurate and high resolution and shorter retention time makes this method more acceptable and cost effective and it can be effectively applied for routine analysis in research institutions, quality control department in meant in industries, approved testing laboratories, bio pharmaceutical and bio equivalence studies and in clinical pharmacokinetic studies in near future.

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Abbreviations:

ACE : Angiotensin Converting Enzyme
RAAS : Rennin Angiotensin Aldosterone System
RSD : Relative Standard Deviation.

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